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**CLOSED-CIRCUIT TELEVISION (CCTV) CAMERAS AND ITS EFFECTIVENESS
IN PREVENTING SHOPLIFTING AND PROMOTING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
IN SELECTED SUPERMARKETS IN UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effectiveness of Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras in the prevention of shoplifting in the supermarkets in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. A sample size of 300 respondents was drawn from over 1000 supermarkets in Uyo using a purposive sampling technique. The population of the study consisted of supermarket operators and their attendants. Data was gathered using both quantitative and qualitative methods. Questionnaire and oral interview were instruments for data collection. Frequency distribution table and simple percentages were used for data presentation and conversational analysis was used in analyzing the qualitative data. The study was guided by the assumption of routine activity theory of Lawrence E. Cohen and Marcus Felson and the rational choice theory of Derek B. Cornish and Ronald V. Clarke. The findings show that majority of respondents have agreed that CCTV surveillance cameras have been very effective in the prevention of shoplifting in the supermarkets but many are yet to have them installed in their supermarkets. Supermarket operators in Uyo are still relying on physical security measures of uniformed security guards in their supermarkets other than CCTV cameras. The study suggested among other things that supermarket operators should accept and use CCTV surveillance cameras as the most effective security measure and install them in their business premises. Government should subsidize the cost of CCTV cameras for supermarket operators. This will go a long way in curbing the rate of crime in the supermarkets.

Keywords: Closed-Circuit, Supermarket, Cameras, Shoplifting and Crime Prevention

INTRODUCTION

Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) camera or devices, otherwise called video surveillance. Kumar and Svensson (2015) in Piza, Welsh, Farrington and Thomas (2019) observed that Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) camera has been a mainstream crime prevention measure used around the world. In 2016, about 350 million surveillance cameras were installed worldwide with 65% of these devices installed in Asia (SDM Magazine, 2016, May 5). In 2018, China was reported to have a huge surveillance network of over 170 million CCTV cameras with 400 million new cameras expected to be installed in the next three years, many of which use facial recognition technology (BBC News, 2018, April 13). In the United Kingdom, Big Brother Watch Report (2012) had it that that the total number of CCTV cameras was 52,000 and the vast majority of CCTV cameras are not operated by government bodies, but by private individuals or companies, especially to monitor the interiors of shops and businesses. In Latin America, the CCTV market is growing rapidly with increase of property crime (Security Magazine, 2009, October 8). In South Africa, due to the high crime rate CCTV surveillance is widely prevalent.

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In Nigeria, Ogunleye, Adewale, Alase and Ogunde (2011) observed that CCTV camera is relatively new and that its effectiveness is not still clear in deterring or reducing crime.

Gill and Spriggs (2005) in their opinion confirmed the importance of Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras as crime prevention and security measure. Gill and Spriggs (2005) further observed that Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras collect images, which are transferred to a monitor recording device of some sort, where they are available to be watched, reviewed or stored. There are many different types of CCTV systems and they have different capacities to meet a variety of objectives (Gill and Spriggs, 2005). In supermarkets, security is the key concern; CCTV cameras can have an impact on the detection and deterrence of internal and external thieves (Kibacia, Kamau and Siror, 2017). With enough cameras, the supermarkets can simultaneously watch for intruders, shoplifters, and dishonest employees throughout the premises (Phillips, 2001). Shoplifting is one of the most prevalent crimes in our society, and it is on the increase in recent years. Krasnovsky and Lane (1998) asserted that shoplifting has received relatively little attention in research literature. In the words of Potdar, Guthrie and Gnoth, (2018), despite huge investments in formal security measures, supermarkets experience shrinkage and face heavy financial losses from shoplifters. Supermarkets are among the places where supervision and security is vital but yet extremely difficult to be maintained (Bandara, n.d). Shoplifters are a problem common to all supermarkets. It is common to see customers stealing items from the supermarkets when someone is around and at the same time when there is no close supervision by the supermarket attendants. Each day, supermarket operators lose so much to shoplifters. The losses are even higher when the supermarket operators have not taken notice of the missing items in their supermarkets and even when they know that these items are missing, the idea of using CCTV camera as a useful crime preventive measure is not considered.

CCTV is that electronic device that is capable of deterring and catching shoplifters or thieves in the supermarkets. CCTV is an anti-theft system control. CCTV deters the supermarket staff from stealing from the supermarket or staff passing goods quickly or easily away to their friends and relatives. It also prevents store rooms from being invaded by thieves. Deterring shoplifters is not the only important function which a professionally installed CCTV system can provide for supermarkets. CCTV can also help both protect and monitor staff activities. In instances where customers become violent and abusive towards the supermarket staff, CCTV camera can play a vital role. In fact, CCTV could help to prevent all such unpleasant incidents. CCTV can offer you the ability to ensure that staff of the supermarkets is properly carrying out their assigned duties (Bandara, n.d). The CCTV cameras could be mounted anywhere within the supermarkets and eliminate all insecure corners. Despite the availability and the benefits of these security cameras, shoplifting remains a major challenge to owners of supermarkets and their attendants (Wikipedia Encyclopedia 2019).

This study therefore, sought to investigate the effectiveness of Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras in the prevention of shoplifting in supermarkets in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Routine Activity theory of Cohen and Felson (1979) and the rational choice theory of Cornish and Clarke (1986) were adopted to explain the phenomenon of shoplifting in the supermarkets.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The general objective of the study is to investigate the effectiveness of Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras in the prevention of shoplifting in supermarkets in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study also has the following specific objectives;

- to compare the pre and post installation periods of CCTV cameras to prevent shoplifting in the supermarkets and
- to investigate the effectiveness of CCTV cameras in preventing shoplifting in the supermarkets in Uyo.

Research Questions

The study has the following research questions;

1. what is the difference between the period operators of supermarkets in Uyo did not use CCTV cameras in preventing shoplifting and now that these CCTV cameras are being installed in the supermarkets?
2. How effective are CCTV Cameras in preventing shoplifting in the supermarkets in Uyo?

LITERATUREREVIEW

In the study, the related literature on the topic under investigation was reviewed. The review of related literature anchored on studies that had been conducted. Theoretical framework also formed part of this work.

What is CCTV Camera?

According to Wikipedia Encyclopedia (n.d), CCTV is the use of video cameras to transmit a signal to a specific place, on a limited set of monitors. It differs from broadcast television in that the signal is not openly transmitted; it may employ point to point (P2P), point to multipoint (P2MP), or mesh wired or wireless links. Though almost all video cameras fit this definition, the term is most often applied to those used for surveillance in areas that may need monitoring such as the supermarkets, banks and other areas where security is needed.

Okere (2012) asserted that CCTV is an important tool for crime prevention and security. Okere (2012) further opined that CCTV cameras has the capacity of collecting images which are transferred to a monitor recording device, where they are available to be watched, reviewed and stored. It is a situational measure that enables an area to be kept under surveillance remotely. In the operations of a CCTV, the availability of light is important for the CCTV camera so as to help the electronic picture production (Cumming, 1994). The specific installation methods that are best for users will depend on the components chosen.

What is shoplifting?

Shoplifting is defined as the theft of items from a retail store with no intention of paying for them (Krasnovsky and Lane, 1998). A shoplifter is an informal term used to define a person found guilty of the theft of items. In a literature review undertaken by Krasnovsky and Lane (1998), shoplifting is discussed as a crime committed regularly and acknowledges an increase in prevalence causing significant harm to society. Although generally, it is believed to be a common and costly crime, the actual extent of retail theft (commonly known as shoplifting) is unknown, largely due to under-reporting and the inaccuracy of retail stock systems (Krasnovsky and Lane 1998).

The effectiveness of CCTV Cameras in preventing shoplifting in supermarkets

Shoplifting is one of the most prevalent crimes in our society, and it is on the increase in recent years. Shoplifting has received relatively little attention in research literature (Krasnovsky and Lane 1998). Most of the people living in insecure areas believe that they may fall under attack any time and become the next victims of the criminal losses. The CCTVs eradicate the fear among the people in order to deter crime occurrence. Presence of the surveillance services assures the people that the surveyed areas are deemed to be more secure than the areas under no surveillance, hence more people access the protected areas compared to the areas without CCTV devices (Gips, 2006). Short and Ditton (1998) in their study found that some offenders were deterred by the presence of CCTV cameras. Those who had been caught on camera were significantly more likely to view CCTV camera as a threat. Perhaps, as more are caught on CCTV camera, and as offenders become aware of this, the threat it is seen to pose will also increase, but the crime rate will definitely reduce.

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Findings from a longitudinal study by Griffiths (2003) suggest that CCTV may effectively deter crime initially within the first year following installation but, that this positive effect is not maintained thereafter. Evidence from Griffiths (2003) suggests that CCTV is the most effective in deterring shoplifting and vehicle theft, the latter being consistent with previous research. Mazzerolle, Hurley and Chamlin (2002 in the Scottish Government, 2009) found some evidence to suggest a deterrence effect of CCTV on anti-social behavior. Bamfield (1994) observed that a large number of retail thefts (approximately 62%) may be perpetrated or facilitated by employees. Determining whether it is staff or customers who are committing the majority of shoplifting offences in a particular store is vital and has direct implications for the type of intervention that should be implemented. For instance, although CCTV may deter customers from shoplifting, employees are usually able to circumvent these security measures (Greenberg and Barling 1996). An important factor that seemed to impact on the effectiveness of interventions was staff attitudes towards the program. Researchers noted complacent staff attitudes towards shoplifting in a number of studies. It appeared that the introduction of security measures in some stores made staff less likely to engage in basic crime prevention measures, such as approaching suspicious customers (Morgan, Boxall, Lindeman and Anderson, 2012).

Research also suggests that retail stores in which staff and management have negative working relationships may have higher rates of employee thefts than stores where these relationships are positive (Greenberg and Barling 1996). When relationships between retail management and staff are negative, employee shoplifting may be legitimized by offenders as 'punishing' the business. Promoting strong, open and positive relationships between staff and management may go some way to addressing employee theft.

In a different opinion, Wilner (2005) observed that in advanced cases especially with the alarm-programmed CCTVs, some activities considered to be criminal might not be detected by the cameras due to the fact that such a crime was not programmed in the CCTV, hence, people can thus commit unique mistakes and crimes and still get away with them because the crimes do not show in the CCTV cameras. This observation by Wilner (2005) does not counter the effectiveness of CCTV cameras, rather, it tells us about some specific type of CCTV cameras that detect crimes that are being programmed into the system through alarms.

THEORETICAL DISCUSSION

The two theoretical perspectives of relevance adopted in the study are the routine activity theory of Lawrence E. Cohen and Marcus Felson (1979) and the rational choice theory of Derek B. Cornish and Ronald V. Clarke (1986). The routine activity theory of Lawrence E. Cohen and Marcus Felson proposes that in order for crime to occur, three elements must occur: the offender must be motivated to commit the crime, the victim must be available and the constraints or checks must be absent. CCTV may actually impact on all three elements: the presence of cameras may reduce the motivation of the offender because of the risk of being caught; the cameras may make victims more security conscious and thus less of an easy target; and the system may allow the police to respond more quickly, making the constraints more effective. Closely linked to routine activity theory is the rational choice approach of Clarke and Cornish which suggests that offenders constantly make choices that have a rational basis. The supermarkets and the attendants (victims) present opportunities for crime and the desire and motivation to commit an offence is weighed up against the risks involved. CCTV may serve to both reduce the opportunities (of free access to persons and property and increase the risks (for example, of being observed and apprehended), with the outcome that a rational decision is taken not to commit an offence. The rational choice theory posits that every normal criminal weighs the risk involved and gains expected before making a choice. This makes the availability of CCTV a preventive instrument for crime control and prevention in the supermarkets.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a cross sectional survey research design. Data was collected using quantitative and qualitative approaches. There are over 1000 supermarkets across the city of Uyo, out of which 300 supermarkets were selected for investigation. The population of the study consisted of supermarkets operators and the supermarket's attendants. The sample size of the study consisted of 300 respondents drawn from the 300 selected supermarkets in Uyo using a purposive sampling technique. The study used self-administered copies of questionnaire and interview methods to collect primary data. To make the data meaningful, the data gathered was analyzed using descriptive statistics. Conversational analysis was also used to analyze the qualitative data.

Data Presentation

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of respondents where 178 (59.33%) are males and 122 (40.67%) are females. Sixty one representing 20.33% of the respondents are between ages 15-20 years, 70 (23.33%), 42 (14%), 28 (9.33%), 32 (10.67%), 31 (10.33%), 36 (12%) are between ages 21-26years, 27-32years, 33-38years, 39-44years, 45-50, 51 years and above respectively. The distributions of their religions are 289 (96.33%) Christians, 3 (1%) Islam, 1 (0.33%) African Traditional Religion, while 7 (2.33%) are adherents of other religions. Also, 18 (6%) of the respondents has first school leaving certificate, 162 (54%) are senior school certificate holders, 120 (40%) are holders of B.Sc., ND, HND and NCE.

Table 1: Demographic Data of the Respondents

Demographic variables	No of Respondents	Percentage
Sex		
Male	178	59.33
Female	122	40.67
Total	300	100
Age (years)		
15-20	61	20.33
21-26	70	23.33
27-32	42	14
33-38	28	9.33
39-44	32	10.67
45-50	31	10.33
51 and above	36	12
Total	300	100
Religion		
Christian	289	96.33
Islam	3	1
African Traditional Religion	1	0.33
Others	7	2.33
Total	300	100
Educational Level		
FSLC	18	6
SSCE	162	54
B.Sc./ND/HND/NCE	120	40
Total	300	100

Source: Field data, 2019

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Table 2: Frequency distribution of respondents according to installation of CCTV cameras in the supermarkets in Uyo

Question	Yes	No	Total
Do you install CCTV cameras in your supermarket?	96 (32%)	204 (68%)	300 (100%)

Source: Field data, 2019

Table 2 shows that 96 respondents representing 32% which formed the minority of the respondents agree to have installed CCTV Cameras in their supermarkets while 204 respondents representing 68% are yet to install CCTV cameras in their supermarkets. This implies that supermarkets installed with CCTV devices are less than those without the installation of CCTV devices.

Table 3: Frequency distribution of respondents according the rate of shoplifting when CCTV cameras were not introduced to supermarket operators in Uyo

Question	High	Very high	Undecided	Low	Very low	Total
How would you rate shoplifting when cctv cameras were not introduced to supermarket operators in Uyo?	107 (35.67%)	188 (62.67%)	2 (0.67%)	1 (0.33%)	2 (0.67%)	300 (100%)

Source: Field data, 2019

Table 3 shows that 188 respondents representing (62.67%) formed the majority who are of the opinion that the rate of shoplifting in the supermarkets was very high when CCTV cameras were not introduced to supermarket operators in Uyo, 107 (35.67%) high, 2 (0.67%) very low, 1 (0.33%) low and 2 (0.67%) choose to be undecided. This result shows that shoplifting in the supermarkets was on increase when there was no installation of CCTV cameras in their Supermarkets in Uyo.

Table 4: Frequency distribution of respondents according the rate of shoplifting after the installation of CCTV cameras in the supermarkets in Uyo

Question	High	Very high	Undecided	Low	Very low	Total
How would you rate shoplifting after installation of CCTVcameras in your supermarkets?	8 (8.33%)	6 (6.25%)	2 (2.08%)	32 (33.33%)	48 (50%)	96 (100%)

Source: Field data, 2019.

In table 4, the question was targeted to those supermarkets operators who have already installed CCTV cameras in their business premises. It reveals that 8(8.33%) respondents are of the opinion that the rate of shoplifting is still high after the installation of CCTV cameras in their supermarkets,

6 (6.25%) respondents say that the rate of shoplifting is very high, 2 (2.08%) respondents are undecided, 32 (33.33%) respondents say that the rate of shoplifting is low, 48 (50%) respondents say that the rate of shoplifting is very low after the installation of CCTV cameras in their supermarkets. This implies that the majority of respondents have agreed that the rate of shoplifting has reduced after the installation of CCTV devices in their supermarkets.

Table 5: Frequency distribution of respondents according to effectiveness of CCTV cameras in preventing shoplifting in the supermarkets in Uyo

Question	Very Ineffective	Ineffective	Undecided	Effective	Very Effective	Total
How effective are CCTV Cameras in preventing shoplifting in the supermarkets?	15 (5%)	18 (6%)	6 (2%)	61 (20.33%)	200 (66.67%)	300 (100%)

Source: Field data, 2019

Table 5 shows that 200 respondents representing 66.67% are of the opinion that CCTV cameras are very effective in preventing shoplifting in the supermarkets in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State; 61 respondents (20.33%) says it is effective, 6 respondents (2%) could not decide on the effectiveness of CCTV cameras in preventing shoplifting in the supermarkets in Uyo, 18 (6%) says that it is ineffective while 15 (5%) says that CCTV cameras are very ineffective in preventing shoplifting in the supermarkets in Uyo. From the responses, majority of respondents have confirmed that the installation of CCTV cameras in the supermarkets in Uyo have been very effective in preventing shoplifting. The above statement indicates that even when minimal number of supermarket operators installed the CCTV device, those who never stalled the CCTV device acknowledged the positive roles of CCTV device in curbing the rate of shoplifting in the supermarkets.

Presentation of Interviews

According to a participant in the interview:

There is no doubt that CCTV surveillance cameras are effective mostly in reducing the rate of shoplifters in my supermarket business. I have been into this business for the past 14 years with many branches across Uyo. If I may tell you, I have lost so many of my goods worth millions of Naira to shoplifters and robbers and this prompted me to install CCTV surveillance cameras all over the branches of the supermarkets that I have. Most times, when the shoplifters know that there is a camera watching their actions, they might likely chose not to commit any criminal act knowing too well that he or she is being watched. I have professionals in place who monitor what is happening on the screen and with this facility on ground; shoplifters can be easily detected and deterred. I have enjoyed using CCTV cameras in my business premises and I therefore recommend it to my colleagues.

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Another supermarket operator in an interview confirmed that:

CCTV cameras have contributed positively to crime reduction in the supermarkets. I have these surveillance cameras and you can see it all over my supermarket, it has helped me a lot. This technology has been able to prove to me that so many of my goods were shoplifted without my knowledge. I have caught so many shoplifters in this supermarket with the help of CCTV cameras, but I refused to report them to the police to avoid having litigations in court. I do not want distraction in my life. I must confess to you that for 4 years now the rate of shoplifting in my supermarket has reduced.

Still, another participant in an interview said that:

I know CCTV surveillance cameras as one of the crime prevention mechanisms but I relied heavily on physical security. I have people who are constantly monitoring the movement of customers in the supermarket for me and I pay them at the end of the month. I am satisfied with the physical security measures for now. Some of my colleagues in the same business that I am doing have mounted these cameras and they have been telling me only about the good side of it mostly when we meet in our meetings. Although, I am yet to install this camera in my business premises, my fear is that I am not a computer literate and the cost of maintenance might overwhelm that of the physical security which I am very familiar with. Agents of these gadgets have submitted their proposals to me in many occasions but I do not see the need for it installation. I am not fully convinced of the effectiveness of CCTV surveillance cameras in the prevention of shoplifting in the supermarkets. For me, uniformed security guards are more effective deterrent than the technological measures of CCTV, possibly because shoplifters will ultimately find a way to circumvent technology, whereas “human” security measures are more difficult to bypass.

FINDINGS/DISCUSSION

The major findings to this study include:

- Majority of respondents have agreed that CCTV surveillance cameras have been very effective in the prevention of shoplifting in the supermarkets. Hence, the rate of shoplifting in the supermarkets has reduced to the barest minimum because of the presence of CCTV cameras.
- Supermarket operators in Uyo are still relying on physical security measures of uniformed security guards in their supermarkets other than CCTV devices.
- In most occasions, shoplifters caught in the act of shoplifting in the supermarkets are not always reported to the police but allowed to go with a caution not come near to the premises again. The reason behind this decision is to reduce the cost of litigations in the business.
- Some of the supermarkets have installed CCTV device but poor maintenance culture has been the reason for its malfunctioning and this has discouraged those who are yet to install.
- CCTV cameras are of categories and the cost of installation and maintenance are exorbitant. This must be the reason most supermarket operators rely on uniform security guards (human) in their business outfits.

The findings of this study have in many dimensions been consistent with previous studies. According to Griffiths (2003), CCTV camera is most effective in preventing and deterring shopliftings and any supermarket having these security gadgets stand the chance of benefiting in the reduction of crime rate. Researchers have confirmed that CCTV cameras are the best protection and security apparatus that serves as a supplement to other available security measures. Okere (2012) in his contribution opined that CCTV has the capacity of collecting images which are transferred to a monitor recording device, where they are available to be watched, reviewed and stored.

At the face of it, CCTV appears as one of the most effective ways to prevent occurrence of crimes in the supermarkets. People with plans to shoplift cannot go ahead because they can appear on the monitoring screens and face trial. Evidence seems circumstantial and accurate when the CCTV cameras function in security. Shoplifting and other crimes can also be reduced due to the feeling of apprehension from the CCTV cameras. However, the CCTV security can yield enormous setbacks especially where they do not have sufficient monitoring. Consequently, the CCTV cameras show the best protection and security are beef up, although they should not function to replace but rather to supplement the existing security systems.

CONCLUSION

It is established in the study that CCTV device is the most effective measure for preventing shoplifting in the supermarkets. Shoplifting is usually perceived as an economic crime and CCTV cameras make a potential shoplifter feel apprehensive. The theoretical approaches taken by this study have enabled a clearer picture of the factors which influence shoplifting behavior in the supermarkets. Indeed, those who shoplift are relatively uncritical of rule-breaking behaviour, they see it as little wrong in taking goods without paying for them, and are more likely to have peers who are neutral or favourable to shoplifting. They perceive shoplifting to be an exciting and rewarding activity, facilitated by a retail environment which provides opportunities for a behaviour which is believed to be relatively easy and risk-free.

RECOMMENDATIONS

For the purpose of this study, the following recommendations were made;

- It was noted that many supermarkets have not fully embraced CCTV surveillance cameras. In order to prevent shoplifting, supermarket operators should accept and use CCTV surveillance cameras as the most effective security measure and install them in their business premises.
- Government should subsidize the cost of CCTV cameras for supermarket operators. With this, the supermarket operators will be able to operate their businesses in a more conducive environment and reciprocate the government by paying the approved taxes and revenues to the government treasury.
- All CCTV surveillance systems should be designed to achieve the set goals. The CCTV system can only be fit for the purposes for which it was installed when it meets (achieves) its design goals. To this end, each camera within the CCTV system must have its angle of coverage, resolution, etc. The correct installation of CCTV equipment is necessary to provide on-going reliability.
- Routine maintenance is necessary to ensure that the CCTV system is in its functional state. In fact, the CCTV cameras have to be inspected and confirmed on daily basis for its efficiency.
- Effort should be made to train people in the area of CCTV device maintenance. Instead of spending much money to bring an electronic engineer from far places to come and maintain the CCTV device, the acquisition of maintenance knowledge and skill would create room for competition and the users of these devices will benefit from such completion thereby reducing the cost of maintenance.

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